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THERAPY**

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
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SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY

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ТЕРАПИЯ

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FEATURES OF NEW HEMOGRAM INDICATORS IN LIVER CIRRHOSIS

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Annotation. Currently modern automated blood analysis systems provide a set of new hemogram indicators, which, in essence, are “research” and require clinical interpretation. For example, flow cytometry - a technology of a number of analyzers of the DYMIND series - significantly expands the possibilities of studying cells of various hematopoietic germs. Using optical detection, the qualitative features of a blood cell are analyzed, depending on the size/volume, internal structure, nucleic acid content (RNA/DNA, maturity and metabolic activity). The diagnostic significance of flow cytometry indicators increases in conditions accompanied by hematological disorders.

Keywords: liver cirrhosis, immature blood cells, reticulocytes, platelets.

Аннотация. В настоящее время современные автоматизированные системы анализа крови предоставляют комплекс новых показателей гемограммы, которые, по сути, «исследовательские» и нуждаются в клинической интерпретации. Так, например, проточная цитофлуориметрия - технология ряда анализаторов серии DYMIND - значительно расширяет возможности исследования клеток различных ростков гемопоэза. При помощи оптической детекции анализируются качественные особенности клетки крови, зависящие от размера/объема, внутренней структуры, содержания нуклеиновых кислот (РНК/ДНК, зрелость и метаболическая активность). Диагностическая значимость показателей проточной цитофлуориметрии возрастает при состояниях, сопровождающихся гематологическими нарушениями.

Ключевые слова: цирроз печени, незрелые клетки крови, ретикулоциты, тромбоциты.

Аннотация. Ҳозирги вақтда замонавий автоматлаштирилган қон таҳлил тизимлари янги гемограмма кўрсаткичлари тўпламини тақдим этади, улар моҳиятига кўра "тадқиқот" бўлиб, клиник талқинни талаб қилади. Масалан, оқим цитофлуориметрияси - DYMIND сериясининг бир қатор анализаторлари технологияси - турли гематопоэтик хужайраларини ўрганиш

имкониятларини сезиларли даражада кенгайтиради. Оптик детектор ёрдамида қон хужайраларининг сифат хусусиятлари, ҳажми, ички тузилиши, нуклеин кислотаси таркибига (РНК/ДНК, етуклик ва метаболик фаоллик) қараб таҳлил қилинади. Гематологик бузилишлар билан кечадиган касалликларда оқим цитофлуорометрия кўрсаткичларининг диагностик аҳамияти чексиздир.

Калит сўзлар: жигар циррози, етилмаган қон хужайралари, ретикулоцитлар, тромбоцитлар.

Liver cirrhosis is a fairly common disease, which in its manifest stage is characterized by dysfunction of three hematopoietic lineages: leukocyte, erythrocyte and platelet. A general blood test in patients with developed liver cirrhosis or liver failure can reveal signs of hemolysis, thrombocytopenia, and leukocytopenia [3].

Regarding blood parameters in liver cirrhosis, information from the specialized literature is fragmentary and contradictory. Abnormal red blood cell counts, particularly increased reticulocytes and decreased hemoglobin concentrations, are known to be associated with an increased risk of death in liver transplantation [11]. There is evidence of both a decrease in the relative number of reticulocytes to 0.79% in the presence of fibrosis in children [6], and an increase in the absolute number of reticulocytes to $0.064 \times 10^{12}/l$ in adults with verified cirrhosis of the liver [9]. A number of authors report a complex disorder of the hemostatic system, including thrombocytopenia [5,8,10]. As for the new indicators of leukocyte, reticulocyte and platelet analysis obtained through laser detection, the question of their informative value in liver cirrhosis remains open.

Purpose of the study: to identify informativethe value of new hemogram indicators obtained using flow cytometry in liver cirrhosis.

Material and methods. The results of a general blood test of individuals in the main and control groups were analyzed. The main group was represented by 64 patients with verified liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia. The structure of cirrhosis was as follows: 38 cases of viral etiology, 24 of nutritional toxicity, 2 of cryptogenic origin. The sample was represented by 30 men and 34 women aged 62.1 ± 39.5 ears. The control group was formed from 70 healthy volunteers undergoing routine preventive examination. The sample was represented by 35 men and 35 women, 55.3 ± 28.7 ears old.

Blood samples were examined on a DYMIND DF-50 analyzer. The following indicators were analyzed: 1) leukocyte: white blood cell count (WBC, $10^9/l$); relative amount of immature granulocytes (IG, %); absolute number of immature granulocytes (IG, $10^9/L$); 2) erythrocyte and reticulocyte: red blood cell count

(RBC, $10^{12}/l$); hematocrit (HCT,%); mean erythrocyte volume (MCV, fl); average hemoglobin content in an erythrocyte (MSI, pg); mean hemoglobin concentration in erythrocytes (MCHC, g/dL); coefficient of variation of erythrocytes by volume (RDW,%); relative number of fragmented red blood cells (Frg,%); relative number of reticulocytes (Ret,%); absolute reticulocyte count (Ret, $10^{12}/l$); relative number of immature reticulocytes (IRF,%); relative numbers of reticulocytes with low, medium and high fluorescence (LFR, %, MFR, % and HFR%); average hemoglobin content in reticulocytes (Ret-He, pg); delta-hemoglobin (D-He, pg); 3) platelet: platelet count measured in impedance mode (PLT, $10^9/l$); platelet count measured in optical mode (PLT-O, $10^9/l$); relative number of immature platelets (IPF,%); coefficient of variation of platelets by volume (PDW,%); mean platelet volume (MPV, fl); percentage of large platelets greater than 12 fL (P-LCR, %); thrombocrit (PCT, %).

The analyzed indicators are divided into two groups: those obtained using conductometric technology (traditional parameters) and flow cytometry (new parameters).

Statistical processing of the data was carried out using the Statistica 7 and Excell 2010 programs. The following statistical parameters were used: M - mean value, Sd - standard deviation, Sd. er. - standard error. Intergroup differences were assessed based on Student's t test at a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$. Statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$) Pearson correlation coefficients (r) were analyzed. To analyze the distribution of indicator values, curves were calculated that display the probability density $p(x)$ (the ratio of probability to the length of the interval) and represent a theoretical analogue of a histogram.

Results and discussions. In table figures 1 and 2 present the results of hemogram analysis in patients with liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia and in the control group.

In accordance with the tables, in patients with cirrhosis, compared with the control group, the number of leukocytes (WBC) was statistically significantly reduced to $5.06 \pm 3.37 \times 10^9/l$, the content of immature granulocytes (IG) was increased to $0.44 \pm 0.77\%$, or $0.04 \pm 0.15 \times 10^9/l$. According to the results of individual analysis, 46.8% of people in the main group leukocytopenia was registered ($WBC < 4.0 \times 10^9/l$).

Table 1.

Traditional indicators of complete blood count in patients with liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia

Indicators	Main group (cirrhosis)	Control group
	<i>M ± Sd(St. er)</i>	
WBC, 10 ⁹ /l	5.06 ± 3.37 (0.42)	7.01 ± 1.81 (0.18)
RBC, 10 ¹² /l	4.02 ± 0.75 (0.09)	4.94 ± 0.53 (0.05)
HGB, g/dl	11.49 ± 2.10 (0.26)	13.95 ± 1.57 (0.16)
HCT, %	36.32 ± 6.02 (0.75)	44.94 ± 3.58 (0.36)
MCV, fl	91.51 ± 11.17 (1.4)*	91.84 ± 3.8 (0.38)*
PLT, 10 ⁹ /l	82.45 ± 30.51 (3.81)	256.03 ± 53.36 (5.31)
RDW, %	16.08 ± 3.05 (0.39)	13.15 ± 0.76 (0.08)
PDW, %	13.31 ± 1.99 (0.29)*	13.17 ± 1.66 (0.17)*
MPV, %	11.19 ± 0.91 (0.13)*	11.08 ± 0.78 (0.08)*
P-LCR, %	34.4 ± 7.27 (1.06)*	33.64 ± 6.82 (0.69)*
PCT, %	0.09 ± 0.03 (0.01)	0.28 ± 0.06 (0.01)

Notenie. Here and in the table. 2: * — intergroup differences are statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

Compared with the control group, the values of traditional erythrocyte parameters (number of erythrocytes, hematocrit level, hemoglobin concentration) in patients with cirrhosis were statistically significantly reduced ($p \leq 0.05$), and the coefficient of variation of erythrocytes by volume was significantly increased (see Table 1). There was no intergroup differences regarding the average volume of erythrocytes ($p > 0.05$). It was found that in liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia, the number of platelets calculated by the impedance method (PLT) was significantly reduced to $82.45 \pm 30.51 \times 10^9/l$ (see Table 1). The platelet content measured in the optical mode of the analyzer (PLT-O) is 10.5% higher than PLT and amounts to $92.08 \pm 32.30 \times 10^9/l$ (see Table 2). Against the background of thrombocytopenia, a statistically significant increase in immature platelets (IPF) to

3.23 ± 1.7% was recorded. According to the results of the correlation analysis, there was an inverse relationship between the content of platelets measured in optical mode and the number of their immature forms ($r = -0.45$).

Table 2.

Flow cytometry indicators in patients with liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia

Indicators	Main group (cirrhosis)	Control group
	<i>M ± Sd(St. er)</i>	
IG, %	0.44 ± 0.77 (0.10)	0.19 ± 0.11 (0.01)
IG, 109/l	0.04 ± 0.15 (0.02)	0.01 ± 0.01 (0.00)
PLT-O, 109/l	92.08 ± 32.30 (4.04)	290.81 ± 61.53 (6.28)
IPF, %	3.23 ± 1.7 (0.22)	1.89 ± 1.16 (0.12)
Ret, %	1.99 ± 1.54 (0.19)	1.10 ± 0.33 (0.03)
Ret, 1012/l	0.07 ± 0.04 (0.00)	0.05 ± 0.02 (0.000)
IRF, %	5.03 ± 4.85 (0.61)	3.35 ± 1.78 (0.18)
LFR, %	94.97 ± 4.84 (0.61)	96.59 ± 1.82 (0.18)
MFR, %	4.56 ± 4.15 (0.52)	3.18 ± 1.67 (0.17)
HFR, %	0.47 ± 0.9 (0.11)	0.18 ± 0.20 (0.02)
Ret-He, pg	29.15 ± 5.52 (0.69)	32.54 ± 1.32 (0.13)
D-He, pg	2.71 ± 1.97 (0.25)*	2.90 ± 0.72 (0.07)*
Frg, %	0.83 ± 1.21 (0.15)	0.10 ± 0.14 (0.01)

Intergroup comparative analysis did not reveal significant differences regarding traditional platelet cell line indicators (PDW, MPV, P-LCR), $p > 0.05$. A statistically

significant decrease in thrombocrit (PCT) in patients with cirrhosis is due to the presence of thrombocytopenia.

In patients of the main group, a statistically significant increase in the relative and absolute content of reticulocytes was registered to 1.99%, or $0.07 \times 10^{12}/l$ (see Table 2). Significant differences were revealed regarding other indicators of reticulocyte analysis. In particular, the content of immature reticulocytes (IRF) in cirrhosis increased to $5.03 \pm 4.85\%$, which is 33.4% higher than the value of the same indicator in the control group. Since the fraction of immature reticulocytes consists of reticulocytes with low and high fluorescence, an increase in IRF is obviously associated with an increase in the proportional contribution of HFR and MFR to the total reticulocyte pool. In general, in liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia, a tendency towards rejuvenation of the reticulocyte formula has been recorded.

In patients of the main group, the average hemoglobin content in reticulocytes (Ret-He) was statistically significantly reduced to 29.15 ± 5.52 pg ($p \leq 0.05$).

It was found that the number of fragmented red blood cells (Frg) in patients with cirrhosis is 88% higher than that of the control group and amounts to $0.83 \pm 1.21\%$.

Laboratory indicators for liver cirrhosis in most cases do not depend on the etiology of the disease and are determined primarily by the level of hepatocellular insufficiency. When assessing liver function, it is common to rely on biochemical tests, while the diagnostic significance of flow cytometry indicators, as a rule, remains outside the scope of clinical interpretation.

It is known that with cirrhosis of the liver, as a rule, all germs of hematopoiesis are affected. The tendency towards leukocytopenia and rejuvenation of the leukoformula revealed as a result of the study corresponds to generally accepted ideas about the mechanisms of impaired granulocytopoiesis in liver dysfunction. Against the background of splenomegaly, which is a frequent companion to cirrhosis, the accelerated destruction of neutrophils and the shortened period of their circulation in the vascular bed cause a decrease in the total content of blood leukocytes. In this case, there is a delay in the maturation of some granulocytes at the stage of promyelocytes, myelocytes or metamyelocytes. Probably, here, according to the “feedback” principle, the decrease in the content of mature blood cells in the periphery is compensated by the accelerated exit of granulocytes, including those of low maturity, from the bone marrow depot.

Thrombocytopenia in liver cirrhosis is a manifestation of hypersplenism and is caused by increased consumption due to increased sequestration, inhibition of megakaryocyte activity and decreased production of thrombopoietin [10]. According to the data obtained, the platelet content measured in the optical unit of

the analyzer (PLO-O) reliably reflected the true number of cells due to the correct identification of giant platelets (with the impedance method, large platelets are mistakenly counted as red blood cells).

Regardless of the genesis, the number of platelets in peripheral blood is regulated in accordance with general biological laws: excess inhibits thrombocytopoiesis, thrombocytopenia stimulates. Indeed, compared with the control group, in cirrhosis, an increase of 41% in the proportional contribution of immature platelets to the total platelet pool was recorded. The increase in IPF indicated that the proliferation processes at the bone marrow level are not impaired, and it is even possible that there is accelerated platelet separation of large platelets, and the genesis of thrombocytopenia is mainly due to the accelerated consumption of cells in the periphery.

It was found that the values of routine platelet analysis indicators (PDW, MPV and P-LCR) did not differ significantly in the main and control groups ($p > 0.05$). The lack of statistically significant correlations with hemogram parameters further neutralized the diagnostic significance of the tests. According to early research results [2], data are provided on the low informative value of P-LCR and MPV in the system of differential diagnosis of thrombocytopenia in pregnant women.

The new research indicator delta-hemoglobin (D-He), which is the mathematical difference between the average hemoglobin content in reticulocytes and the average hemoglobin content in erythrocytes, deserves special attention. In healthy people, the D-He value is always positive and fluctuates in the range of 2-4 pg. Negative D-He values are uncommon, for example in anemia of chronic diseases. In case of inflammation, hepcidin, synthesized by the liver, blocks the transfer of iron by transferrin, which leads to a deficiency of iron available for erythropoiesis [12].

According to the data obtained, pathologically high or low values ($2 \text{ pg} > \text{D-He} > 4 \text{ pg}$) were recorded in 46% of cases of liver cirrhosis. In a small proportion of patients (6.3%) $\text{D-He} < 0$. Negative D-He values are apparently due to concomitant inflammation. In conditions of impaired synthetic function of the liver, a statistically significant decrease in the hemoglobin content in reticulocytes (Ret-He) indicated the limitation of iron for hematopoietic needs and generally confirmed the above trend.

Changes in the functional characteristics of red blood cells in liver pathology are not limited to reticulocytes. At the same time, disturbances occur at the level of mature red blood cells. At high values of delta hemoglobin ($\text{D-He} > 4 \text{ pg}$), reticulocytes are saturated with iron. And in the genesis of the disorder, the mechanisms of hemolysis in the peripheral bloodstream and destruction of functionally defective red blood cells in the spleen take first place. The latter is due

to the fact that in cirrhosis the synthesis of metabolites necessary for erythropoiesis, including vitamin B12, is impaired. Therefore, individual lines of erythrocytes are represented by hemoglobinized megalocytes: functionally inferior, short-lived and osmotically unstable.

Thus, in patients with cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia, the platelet content measured in the optical mode (PLT-O) is 10.5% higher than that calculated by the impedance method. In the case of critically low platelet concentrations, it seems advisable to focus on the PLT-O indicator as the most adequately reflecting the true platelet count. The number of immature platelets in patients with liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia was statistically significantly increased to $3.23 \pm 1.7\%$, which indicates activation of bone marrow thrombocytopoiesis. The degree of “demand” for immature cells is regulated by the feedback principle.

Estimated indicators platelet analysis (PDW, MPV and P-LCR) do not provide additional information characterizing the features of thrombocytopoiesis in liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia. It has been established that in liver cirrhosis there is a dissociation between the content of leukocytes and the number of immature granulocytes: the tendency of leukocytopenia is accompanied by a “left shift” of the leukocyte formula. Compared with the control group, in liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia, the relative and absolute number of reticulocytes was statistically significantly increased, the average hemoglobin content in reticulocytes was reduced, and the reticulocyte formula was rejuvenated ($p \leq 0.5$). Delta-hemoglobin (D-He) in liver cirrhosis associated with thrombocytopenia takes on both positive and negative values. Negative D-He values are associated with an accompanying inflammatory component. A direct relationship was revealed between D-He and the hemoglobin content in reticulocytes ($r = 0.57$), D-He and the number of immature granulocytes ($r = 0.45$). In liver cirrhosis, a statistically significant increase compared to the norm in the average content of phragmetocytes ($0.83 \pm 1.21\%$) and/or the level of delta hemoglobin (D-He > 4 pg) is probably due to the concomitant hemolytic component, characteristic of liver pathology.

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